

Digital Reporting Pathways in Saarland's Drinking Water Surveillance

Opportunities and Risks of an Integrated, Proprietary Specialist Platform for Inter-Agency Collaboration in the Public Health Service

As the open-source debate gathers pace in German public administration, Saarland demonstrates how an integrated specialist platform can connect the Public Health Service and how this architecture can be linked step by step with SHAPTH, the new national data exchange format for drinking water analyses.

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The **Wasserhygienetage** in Bad Elster is an annual specialist conference organised by WaBoLu e. V. in cooperation with the German Environment Agency (UBA). It brings together researchers, practitioners and public authorities to discuss current issues in water hygiene and drinking water surveillance. In 2026, the conference will focus on “50 Years of the German Drinking Water Ordinance” and on new requirements for reporting and local implementation.

This paper serves as **background** for a panel presentation on 5 February, which will focus on a selected aspect of the platform approach described in this contribution.

1 Introduction

1.1 The Guiding Vision of Citizen-Oriented Drinking Water Information

Imagine a hot summer's day. You stop at a public drinking water fountain at the edge of a hiking trail. A QR code is embedded in the stainless steel column, ready to be scanned with your mobile phone, as shown in Figure 1.

On your screen, the Füllpunkt_Saar website opens. It displays the locations and water quality data of all public drinking water fountains in Saarland, along with information on the operator and

the responsible local public health authority.

This fictional example combines a citizen-oriented transparency approach with the information needs of political leadership and the supervisory authority in the context of drinking water surveillance. Conventional reporting on drinking water quality, however, has so far provided the federal state level with access primarily to data from the previous year. While this may suffice for identifying long-term trends, it offers limited value for ongoing specialist supervision.

There is also a structural constraint in the current reporting set-up. Unlike official, authority-commissioned sampling, private analyses relevant to Füllpunkt_Saar are typically transmitted to local public health authorities only when parametric values are exceeded. Fully compliant results therefore often remain with operators, even though a portal such as Füllpunkt_Saar also depends on compliant findings to present a balanced picture of drinking water quality.

Against this backdrop, the example of the digital drinking water fountain frames the guiding question: how can drinking water analyses be routed across different administrative levels in near real time, while at the same time

Fig. 1: Drinking-water fountain of the fictional Füllpunkt_Saar project (illustrative image).

Source: author's own illustration.

enabling new forms of transparency?

At the centre of this exploration is the platform architecture of an integrated digital reporting pathway between Saarland's six local public health authorities and the federal state level. This system is designed to support both specialist supervision and compliance with a new EU reporting format.

This paper explores the strategic decisions associated with this approach, the opportunities it offers, and the potential risks of a proprietary specialist platform, within the broader debate on open standards and open source.

1.2 Federal Starting Point and Governance Challenge

Drinking water surveillance is part of essential public services (Daseinsvorsorge) and public health provision (Eibenstein, 2022,

p. 594). It operates within a framework shaped by EU law, federal legislation and local implementation. The EU Drinking Water Directive sets quality standards and reporting obligations. Federal legislation governs national transposition. Local public health authorities implement the rules on the ground. Between these levels, the federal state authority acts in a supervisory capacity, while operators, water suppliers and laboratories organise sampling and analysis. Responsibilities and tasks are therefore spread across several tiers.

The digital transformation of these structures is taking place within a politically dense federal system, characterised by multiple veto players. This constellation can lead to rigidity and limited flexibility in decision-making processes (Kuhlmann et al., 2025, pp. 93–94). The challenges of implementing digital initiatives under these conditions are exemplified by the Online Access Act (Onlinezugangsgesetz), which is widely considered to have fallen short of its own objectives (Kuhlmann et al., 2025, pp. 308–309).

Expectations of digital transformation go well beyond individual applications or websites and require a fundamental reorientation of administrative processes and services (Boockmann et al., 2025, p. 11). Digitalisation also demands standardisation. In federal systems, this creates a tension between uniform processes and the autonomy of decentralised units (Klenk et al., 2025, p. 938).

While funding programmes such as the Pact for the Public Health Service provide financial impetus, they do not alter the fact that new solutions are only effective when architecture and responsibilities are aligned across all levels.

This results in a dual governance challenge in the drinking water sector. Reporting obligations to federal and EU levels must be

fulfilled without creating additional administrative burden at local level. At the same time, the same data pathways must be designed to support ongoing specialist supervision, crisis management and strategic decision-making.

In a political system where the Länder retain responsibility for specialist supervision and municipalities exercise local self-government (kommunale Selbstverwaltung), tackling this challenge is, above all, a question of digital architecture.

2. Saarland's Digital Strategy

2.1 Digital Maturity Compared Across Federal States

In one key respect, the starting position of Saarland's Public Health Service (ÖGD) differs from that of many other German federal states. In the most recent nationwide assessment of the digital maturity of local public health authorities (Gesundheitsämter), Eymann et al. (2024, pp. 9–10) identify a clear and continuous rise for Saarland.

As shown in Figure 2, the state's scores increase from a low level in 2021 to the highest maturity level by 2024. This observation indicates that digital reporting pathways in drinking water surveillance did not emerge as an isolated measure, but are built on an already consolidated strategic foundation. The integrated specialist platform described below therefore fits into a high level of digital maturity and into the digital strategy outlined in the following sections.

2.2 From Individual Procurements to a Platform Strategy (2016 to 2024)

As early as 2016, Saarland recognised that robust data structures are a prerequisite for sustainable digitalisation in the Public Health Service, and the focus shifted towards the creation of a shared digital working environment. A steering group prepared the deployment of a uniform system, initially conceived as a specialist application (Fachverfahren), and worked towards intermunicipal standards for data capture. With its introduction from 2018 across all six local public health authorities, this approach became binding, as it established the foundation for a shared digital working environment.

Already in the year of its introduction, all drinking water surveillance data could be recorded within the specialist platform, and supervisory tasks were accelerated through paperless processing in field operations (Naundorf, 2021, pp. 4–6).

During the COVID-19 pandemic, additional modules were added, interfaces expanded, and initial process chains automated. Since 2021, this direction has been continued institutionally by the Working Group on Digital Development in the Public Health Service (Arbeitsgruppe Digitale Weiterentwicklung ÖGD), anchored within the Saarland County Association (Landkreistag Saarland). This group replaced the earlier intermunicipal steering committee and now provides coordinated

Fig. 2: Digital maturity development in the digitalisation strategy dimension.

year	BW	BY	BE	BB	HB	HH	HE	MV	NH	NW	RP	Saarland	SN	ST	SH	TH
2021	-1	-1	-1	-1	-1	0	-1	-1	-1	-1	-1	1	-1	-1	-1	-1
2022	0	0	-1	0	-1	0	0	-1	0	0	-1	2	-1	-1	-1	-1
2023	1	1	-1	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	2	1	0	1	0
2024	3	2	1	2	2	0	1	1	2	1	1	4	3	2	2	2

Source: author's own illustration based on data from Eymann et al. (2024).

support to local public health authorities in their digital development (Landkreistag Saarland, 2022).

In parallel, the state programme Digitalisation 4.0 of Saarland's Public Health Service (Digitalisierung 4.0 des saarländischen ÖGD) brings together the expansion steps at state level. Its objectives include modular development of the specialist platform, establishing Digital Scouts as IT staff with needs-focused expertise who actively support and advise local public health authorities in implementing digitalisation projects, and achieving an interoperable, secure and citizen-oriented infrastructure by the end of 2026 (Digitales Gesundheitsamt, 2026).

In retrospect, a **long term direction** becomes visible that can now be described as a platform strategy. All local public health authorities work on the same integrated specialist platform and apply a shared case model (Fallverständnis) as well as the same core functions. This simplifies training, cover arrangements and workflows, and anchors local drinking water enforcement processes within a shared platform core.

2.3 Strategic Positioning: The Platform as an Emergent Digital Strategy

Strategy Terms

Long-term direction refers to the overall orientation of an organisation over time, beyond individual projects (Whittington et al., 2023, p. 6).

Emergent strategy describes a pattern of many individual decisions that only becomes visible as a coherent whole in retrospect (Mintzberg, 1987).

Strategic fit refers to the alignment between strategic direction and organisational structure, creating a coherent and effective overall model (Ansoff, 1965; Chandler, 1962).

Strategy is often associated with large-scale programmes imposed

from the top down. In Saarland, however, the strategy appears to have evolved as an **emergent pattern**, a sequence of recurring decisions made by operational stakeholders in response to practical constraints and efforts to achieve greater harmonisation.

Only in hindsight can these pragmatic steps be recognised as part of a strategic direction. The focus in 2016 was not on creating a comprehensive platform vision, but rather on the realisation that data quality is essential for sustainable digitalisation.

From a strategic perspective, the measures outlined in Section 2.2, the introduction of a shared system, the gradual expansion of modules and interfaces, and increasing automation, form an emergent pattern that becomes recognisable as a platform logic only in hindsight. The result is a near end-to-end digital pathway for data and reporting. The integrated specialist platform has since been described as an “integrated and future-proof digital solution” for Saarland's local public health authorities and as an “example of successful administrative digitalisation” (Arbeitsgemeinschaft der Obersten Landesgesundheitsbehörden – AOLG, 2025, pp. 13–14).

A recent practice report also shows that this development now extends to a platform-integrated, near-real-time reporting layer, in which automated data flows between local public health authorities and the supervisory authority at federal state level complement previous annual reporting. This enables decisions to be based on continuously updated data (Rausch and Wagner, 2025, pp. 51–63).

Viewed in this way, the integrated specialist platform is less a product than a framework for working practices, data flows and inter-agency collaboration. It brings technology, routines and

cooperation together in a shared environment and is likely difficult to replicate, as it is closely embedded in the established practices of Saarland's local public health authorities.

This places **strategic fit** at the centre of the analysis. What matters is whether the platform logic and the organisational design combine to form a coherent overall model. The following section positions this development within the **OECD digital government framework**, provides initial indications of this alignment, and prepares the ground for the governance issues discussed in Chapter 5.

2.4 Positioning Within the OECD Framework Model

The developments outlined above align closely with three selected dimensions of the OECD framework model for digital government.

Digital Government Framework

Three relevant dimensions:

Digital by design: workflows are conceived to function effectively in digital form from the outset, with no need for later adaptation (OECD, 2020, p. 11).

Data-driven public sector: data is treated as a strategic asset to improve decisions and accelerate administrative action (OECD, 2020, pp. 14–17).

Government as a platform: shared digital components reduce complexity and enable more consistent public service delivery across levels (OECD, 2020, pp. 20–24).

In the local implementation of the German Drinking Water Ordinance, **digital by design** is reflected in the way new requirements are conceived from the outset so that they can be captured directly in the integrated specialist platform. The water module emerged from the day-to-day practice of local public health authorities and links monitoring programmes, drinking water facilities

and the documentation of administrative interventions into a seamless digital workflow. Complex evaluations, automatically generated administrative acts (Verwaltungsakte) and web forms are produced directly and efficiently from the recorded cases.

Uniform data capture across all local authorities provides a shared foundation on which a **data-driven public sector** can operate effectively. Reports, dashboards and situational pictures are generated from digitally managed cases without repeated data entry. Workflows align more easily, and specialist requirements can be derived directly from the available data. The integrated specialist platform thus becomes the operational data foundation that supports specialist supervision, crisis management and specialist steering.

Within the Public Health Service, Saarland's architecture also functions as a shared technical backbone. The integrated specialist platform provides core functions such as case creation (Fallanlage), documentation, deadline management (Fristensteuerung) and reporting on which different functional areas can build.

At the federal state level, a dedicated platform instance complements these local structures, forming a shared reporting layer built on the same data foundation. In this combination of shared components and varied use cases, the concept of **Government as a Platform (GaaP)** becomes tangible. In Saarland, it is translated into a concrete area of local implementation and is further developed in the next chapter through the digital reporting pathway.

3. Reporting Pathway Architecture

3.1 Decentralised Architecture and Web Service

The platform architecture is based on a decentralised model,

comprising local platform instances within each local public health authority and a reporting layer at federal state level. Each local public health authority operates its own platform instance with a dedicated database, while the supervisory authority maintains a separate federal state platform instance. A proprietary web service forms the core of the digital reporting pathway, transferring specialist-validated cases from local authorities to the supervisory authority and thereby establishing an end-to-end digital reporting pathway.

This web service enables largely automated transfer of monitoring plans, parametric value exceedances and other reportable events into the administrative data holdings at federal state level. It also supports encrypted exchanges of administrative documentation, follow-up reminders and complete digital case files. This allows local public health authorities to share cases with one another when necessary (Rausch and Wagner, 2025, pp. 48, 51).

Figure 3 illustrates how local public health authorities are connected to the federal state reporting layer via the proprietary web service.

3.2 From Annual Reporting to Near-Real-Time Reporting

Traditionally, reporting on drinking water quality followed a fixed annual cycle. Water suppliers and laboratories submitted their results to local public health authorities, where the data was reviewed and consolidated into annual reports. These overviews were then forwarded to federal state level, from where aggregated reports were submitted to the next administrative tier (Kleber and Busskamp, 2011).

Near real time reporting refers to low latency data availability within the day and is commonly achieved through frequent refresh cycles rather than continuous streaming. (Baars & Kemper, 2021, p. 43).

Operational definition in this paper refers to an automated push and pull rhythm that results in a reporting layer with a maximum data latency of up to six hours in routine operation. The web service is the data pathway, while the reporting layer and situational picture constitute operational business intelligence rather than mere data transport. (Stoi & Dillerup, 2022, p. 790).

With the introduction of the proprietary web service, the reporting

Source: author's own illustration.

rhythm in Saarland has shifted. Analyses and specialist-validated case data now flow continuously and automatically into the federal state platform instance. Instead of relying on year-end consolidation, a continuously updated situational picture is generated. It can be accessed at any time without additional preparation and provides **near-real-time** visibility of ongoing cases.

This shifts drinking water surveillance away from retrospective documentation and towards a practical basis for ongoing specialist supervision and operational decision-making. Formal reporting obligations remain unchanged, but the data can now be used in day-to-day practice as a basis for specialist supervision and operational decision-making.

3.3 Contribution to Reporting to the EU Level

The digital reporting pathway between local and federal state levels also provides the foundation for reporting Saarland's drinking water data to federal and EU levels.

Previously, data from local public health authorities was compiled in Excel spreadsheets, sent by email to federal state level, and manually consolidated into a state-level report, which was then incorporated into the national submission.

Fig. 4: Opportunity compass of the integrated platform.

Source: author's own illustration.

According to a recent practice report, under this previous approach, the oldest analysis from 2024 would only have been included in federal reporting 605 days later (Rausch and Wagner, 2025, p. 47).

With the introduction of a platform-integrated reporting layer, the data required for EU-level reporting is now continuously available in a structured format. Monitoring plans, analyses, parametric value exceedances and associated measures are recorded once by local public health authorities and can be compiled into reporting packages at federal state level without requiring year-end consolidation.

As a result, the underlying data pathway has shifted from one-off compilation at year-end to a continuously maintained data foundation, from which reports to federal and EU levels could be generated at defined reporting dates.

4. Opportunities and Risks of an Integrated Platform

4.1 Methodology

The analysis of opportunities and risks follows a theory-driven compass with four impact dimensions, as shown in Figure 4. For each dimension, potential benefits and corresponding tensions were considered.

The literature review followed a scoping-oriented approach. Relevant conceptual fields relating to administrative digitalisation, platforms and public sector governance served as starting points. All selected sources were documented in an analysis table. Each entry included (a) page references for the relevant impact dimension, (b) a brief justification of the

source's relevance, and (c) an assessment of its transferability to the Saarland case. Less suitable references were excluded, and the remaining material was coded as indicators of opportunity or risk.

The analysis is qualitative and interpretative in nature and does not claim completeness. Rather, the selected studies serve as an interpretive framework for positioning routines, system architecture and data flows in the Saarland case. Finally, the central findings for each impact dimension were condensed into a small number of concise theses, each supported in the paper by selected quotations from the literature.

4.2 Opportunities of the Integrated Platform Architecture Approach

Continuously Updated Situational Picture at the Federal State Level

A continuously updated situational picture enables drinking water specialist supervision to be managed as an ongoing process rather than being limited to periodic reporting. Schmeling et al. (2019, p. 5) emphasise that evidence-based steering depends on continuous monitoring of strategically defined indicators and regular evaluations. Continuous updates make deviations and patterns visible at an early stage, while cases are still open and corrective measures can still be taken. The situational picture consolidates dispersed data into a shared, decision-relevant overview for the supervisory authority. This not only makes parametric value exceedances visible, but also enables tracking of which measures have been documented and where entries are missing. In this way, documentation gaps can be addressed and approaches harmonised across local public health authorities. Organisational steering and monitoring systems embedded within specialist applications and implemented via integrated

data platforms appear particularly well suited to this purpose (Schmeling et al., 2019, pp. 3–4, 17).

From this perspective, an up-to-date situational picture increases the capacity for timely, data-driven decisions. Schopp et al. (2022, pp. 1–2, 5) describe situational pictures as both a foundation for decision-making and an essential tool beyond crisis contexts. International experience likewise shows that performance dashboards updated regularly, or even daily, have become key instruments in modern public sector management (Shostak et al., 2023, pp. 94–95).

Relief for the Operational Levels

The approach also aims to consolidate reporting obligations while simplifying day-to-day communication with the supervisory authority. Local public health authorities record cases and associated measures once in the system, eliminating the need for parallel notifications and additional emails containing identical information. Empirical studies show that e-government procedures can reduce processing times and lower staff stress and workload (Al-Hussein et al., 2023, p. 1668), and that automated rather than manual data transfers significantly reduce search, communication and transaction times (Arendsen et al., 2014, pp. 162–163). Applied to drinking water specialist supervision, it can be expected that routine tasks such as notifications, follow-up enquiries and reporting are likely to be streamlined.

Inter-Agency Collaboration in the Public Health Service (ÖGD)

The integrated platform also facilitates inter-agency collaboration within a shared digital working environment. Cases, samples and measures are documented in a uniform system and processed using consistent routines. A shared data model and standardised data capture enable reliable

comparability. In the literature, such cross-organisational approaches are described as collaboration strategies that align workflows and service delivery across institutional boundaries, thereby enabling joint implementation (Bunger et al., 2024, pp. 2–3; Chuang et al., 2024, p. 2).

Using the example of local public health authorities, Reeder et al. (2014, pp. 183–184, 187–189) show that integrated information systems based on single data entry support collaboration both within and beyond the organisation, as the data can be reused for reporting, coordination and communication with partners. Studies in digital government view such platforms as forms of inter-agency collaboration that create information systems capable of enabling data exchange and functional interoperability across public authorities (Fedorowicz et al., 2014, p. 302).

Added Value of Future-Proof and Interoperable Data

Additional value arises through the creation of future-proof and interoperable data for emerging requirements. Using the example of German municipalities, Fritz (2020, pp. 12–13) identifies increasing demands under constrained resources as a reason why strategic data management is becoming a “key topic for the future”, with interoperability and standardised data structures as essential components.

In Saarland's case, parts of this foundation are already in place through consistent structures. While other administrations still need to harmonise data capture methods, exchange formats and interfaces, Saarland is already working within a functioning platform ecosystem. At the same time, the platform reduces redundant submissions by capturing centrally what was previously transmitted in parallel via the specialist application and additional

communications. This reflects the core idea of the once-only principle (Wimmer and Marinov, 2017, pp. 1–2).

This creates a robust foundation for future reporting obligations and emerging data spaces. Data on samples, measures and drinking water infrastructure is uniformly structured and can be channelled into higher-level reporting systems at federal and EU levels, or into citizen-oriented information portals, without the need for further data collection or reformatting.

Studies in public health IT confirm that integrated platform architecture supports future data usage and helps avoid unnecessary integration challenges, as such systems are built from the outset on shared structures and a system-wide perspective (Vest et al., 2012, pp. 1–2).

4.3 Risks and Tensions in the Federal Multi-Level System

The integrated platform architecture opens up new opportunities, but it also introduces shared dependencies. Where compatibility was previously achieved through coordination and human mediation, a common technical and organisational framework now takes shape. While this facilitates steering and inter-agency collaboration, it also shifts risk from individual specialist applications to the structure of the overall system. As a result, several key tensions emerge.

Interoperability, Security and Technical Debt

One such tension relates to interoperability, security and technical debt. Alongside drinking water specialist supervision, the platform approach also integrates infectious disease control procedures such as SurvNet@RKI and DEMIS. This reveals dependencies on synchronised interfaces and aligned software versions. Interoperability refers to the ability to

exchange and reuse information between public authorities (Guijarro, 2007, p. 174).

In practice, the exchange of case data functions reliably only if all parties use the same software version. Until then, workarounds and additional coordination are required. Analyses of legacy systems and technical debt show that historically grown dependencies between specialist applications and underlying infrastructure limit interoperability and make modernisation both risky and costly (Irani et al., 2023, pp. 1–2). Nielsen and Madsen (2022, pp. 1–2) describe technical debt as a structural barrier to digital government.

In the context of drinking water specialist supervision, it is therefore plausible that software version mismatches, together with the coordination burden associated with updates and their timing, may increase the system's vulnerability to disruption.

Unequal Starting Points and Additional Burdens

A further issue arises from unequal starting points and the additional burdens associated with introducing such a platform. Platform solutions do not automatically reduce workloads at the operational level. Instead, they tend to shift tasks into new digital routines and initially generate learning and transition costs. Studies on administrative burden show that learning and compliance costs are higher where resources and digital skills are limited (Halling and Baekgaard, 2024, pp. 186–188; Madsen et al., 2022, pp. 6–7). Without adequate support measures, digital-by-default strategies risk reinforcing existing structural inequalities (De Figueiredo and Cortez Da Cunha Cruz, 2025, pp. 2–3; Giest and Samuels, 2023, pp. 626–627, 636).

Applied to the Public Health Service (ÖGD), it can be expected that an integrated digital reporting

pathway will initially place additional demands on already overstretched local public health authorities, before the benefits of standardisation and data reuse are fully realised.

Transparency, Performance Pressure and Rules for Steering

A uniform situational picture alters the relationship between supervisory authorities and local implementation. Studies on local performance regimes show that comparable indicators can strengthen hierarchical control and expose lower-performing authorities to increased scrutiny and intervention (Grubnic and Woods, 2009, pp. 445, 449–452). Research on open data, transparency and digital data infrastructures suggests that the visibility of administrative data alone does not ensure balanced accountability. This requires mechanisms to contextualise deviations and supportive structures (Lourenço et al., 2017, PDF p. 3; Peeters & Widlak, 2018, pp. 175, 181).

In the context of drinking water specialist supervision, there is therefore a risk that the new situational picture may function as a performance regime before adequate rules and resources for shared governance have been established.

Vendor Lock-In and Limited Switching Options

Finally, vendor lock-in and limited switching options represent a structural risk. With each additional specialist function, integration capacity increases, but so does dependence on the chosen provider. High switching costs strengthen the market power of incumbent vendors, as locked-in customers face significant barriers when attempting to adopt alternative solutions (Klemperer, 1995, p. 515). A lack of standardisation and the use of proprietary interfaces make vendor lock-in a serious obstacle to adoption and can render migrations both

technically and organisationally risky (Opara-Martins et al., 2016, pp. 1–3). This becomes particularly critical when core functionalities, such as the digital reporting pathway, rely exclusively on a proprietary web service, where any modification or shutdown would have an immediate operational impact.

Case studies in European procurement law show that, without contractually secured rights to modify and migrate, public sector clients can become fully dependent on their original provider, entering vendor lock-in at an early stage (Svoboda, 2022, pp. 119–121). By contrast, open standards aim to decouple data and documents from specific systems, ensuring long-term usability across platforms and gradually reducing dependence on a single vendor (Lundell and Lings, 2010, pp. 177–178).

Applied to drinking water and infectious disease specialist supervision, this creates the risk that further development or replacement of the platform may only be feasible with considerable effort and in close collaboration with a single incumbent vendor.

These risks do not negate the benefits of the integrated platform approach. Rather, they highlight the areas where particular attention is required, especially with regard to platform governance, which is the focus of the discussion in Chapter 5.

5. Discussion

5.1 Positioning the Compass Within the Strategic Framing

The compass used in Chapter 4 is not a theoretical model in its own right. Rather, it translates the strategic framing from Sections 2 and 3 into four concrete impact dimensions. It builds on the positioning of the platform as an emergent strategy, on the strategic concepts of long-term direction and strategic fit, and on the OECD framework model for digital government.

The current situational picture dimension addresses how the integrated specialist platform strengthens the role of a data-based situation centre for the supervisory authority at federal state level. Relief for the operational levels reflects the principle that digital strategies only succeed if they reduce existing burdens in local implementation. Inter-agency collaboration captures the concept of platform-based public administration, in which shared building blocks support cooperation and interoperability across levels. Future-proof and interoperable data links the logic of a data-driven public sector with the evolving requirements of reporting obligations and emerging data spaces.

From this perspective, the compass is not a neutral evaluation tool. It serves as an analytical instrument for examining Saarland's platform architecture. In Section 4.2, it highlights where the integrated approach reinforces the platform strategy outlined earlier. In Section 4.3, it shows where risks arise from that same architectural model.

At the heart of the discussion lies a core tension running through all four dimensions. The platform derives its strength from a high degree of integration and standardised routines, yet this very integration results in a high level of vendor lock-in with limited switching options. The following sections explore the conditions under which such lock-in might be seen not simply as a rigid dependency, but as a deliberately managed strategic resource.

5.2 From Risk to Strength in Vendor Lock-In

Dependence on a single vendor is often perceived as a weakness in digital government, as it can reduce flexibility and make switching to alternative providers difficult. Analyses of switching costs show that such dependencies increase the market power of

incumbent providers, as locked-in customers can only migrate at considerable cost (Klemperer, 1995, p. 515). Studies on cloud and platform environments similarly describe vendor lock-in as a major barrier to adoption, since migrations are often seen as technically and organisationally risky (Opar-Martins et al., 2016, pp. 1–3). It is therefore understandable that close reliance on a single platform vendor is initially viewed as a risk in Saarland.

In this case, however, the lock-in did not arise by chance. It is the outcome of a long-term platform strategy (see Section 2.3). Instead of maintaining multiple isolated specialist applications with separate interfaces, user interfaces and service providers, the Saarland approach consolidates drinking water specialist supervision within a shared system. This reduces the number of tools staff must navigate, standardises routines and data structures, and simplifies coordination between local platform instances and the federal state level. From this perspective, vendor lock-in is the flip side of deliberate architectural standardisation.

Vendor lock-in only becomes a strategic strength if it is actively managed. This includes ensuring that key rights to data, formats and interfaces do not remain exclusively with the vendor, but are contractually secured for the public sector, for example through clauses on data portability, export mechanisms and migration scenarios. Open standards at the data level can also ensure that documents and domain-specific datasets remain usable in other systems over time (Lundell and Lings, 2010, pp. 177–178).

Under these conditions, close vendor lock-in within an integrated platform can provide a stable foundation for operating complex digital reporting pathways reliably, while still leaving scope for

gradual openness through open interfaces and modular extensions. The next section explores these safeguards in more detail.

5.3 Implications for Open Source and Platform Governance

This paper follows the **OECD definition of Digital Public Infrastructure (DPI)**. In terms of platform governance, this means that the state must coordinate collective action not only through procurement, but also by providing shared tools, managing resources and safeguarding public value (Janowski et al., 2018, p. S2).

DPI – Digital Public Infrastructure
DPI refers to foundational digital systems made up of shared, secure and interoperable components. As reusable building blocks, they support administrative processes and services across different policy areas and help mitigate vendor lock-in risks. The public sector plays a key role in designing, maintaining and governing these infrastructures, and can integrate Digital Public Goods such as open source software, open standards and open data (OECD, 2024, pp. 6–8).

In the Saarland case, elements of this DPI logic are already realised within the integrated specialist platform. Its architecture consolidates drinking water specialist supervision within a shared system, applies uniform data models, and adheres to the once-only principle for data entry (Wimmer and Marinov, 2017). This creates a domain-specific base infrastructure upon which additional applications can be built, for example SHAPTH or citizen-oriented drinking water information services.

Although the proprietary platform solution does limit competition in the vendor market, it does not necessarily restrict openness in other areas, provided that data exchange formats, interfaces and export mechanisms are transparent and contractually secured.

This does not lead to a simple

recommendation either for or against open source. Instead, open standards and open formats remain essential because they reduce long-term dependency on specific systems and ensure that data remains usable across different platforms (Lundell and Lings, 2010, p. 179). As a result, **platform governance** becomes the central issue.

Open-source components can be particularly valuable in areas such as data exchange formats, APIs, analytical tools and citizen-oriented drinking water information services. A proprietary platform core can still be part of a digital public infrastructure if its public function is secured through governance structures and contractual safeguards. What matters is that data sovereignty, exit options and the future development of the platform are not entirely controlled by the vendor.

In this paper, the shared management of the platform is referred to as **governance**. This includes the clear definition of roles and responsibilities, formal procedures and decision-making rules, the structuring of contracts with vendors, and the creation of coordination bodies in which the federal state level, counties and operators jointly steer the platform's operations and further development.

The opportunities and risks discussed suggest that strategic sovereignty depends less on whether the source code is publicly available, and more on whether the public sector plays an active role in shaping the platform's direction. This involves setting binding standards for data management, system migration and interoperability. From this perspective, the Saarland approach argues not for a binary decision between open and proprietary solutions, but for a deliberately governed mix, combining proprietary components, open standards and selected open-source elements in a

balanced and future-oriented way.

5.4 Limitations , Transferability

This paper is intended as an analytical practice report and is subject to several limitations. It examines a single case and interprets Saarland's platform architecture primarily as a strategic and organisational constellation rather than as a fully evaluated intervention. Quantitative effects on processing times, workload or error rates are not systematically measured. Instead, they are inferred from the system architecture, observed operational routines, and referenced studies on e-government, administrative burden and public health IT discussed in the preceding chapters. The analysis therefore does not replace formal impact monitoring in the strict sense.

At the same time, the case is closely tied to Saarland's specific starting conditions. As a small federal state with a limited number of local public health authorities, a platform strategy developed over several years, and well-established structures for the digital development of the Public Health Service (ÖGD), Saarland differs markedly from environments characterised by many specialist applications, varying levels of digital maturity and only emerging interoperability strategies. The near-universal use of a shared platform, the close coordination between state and county levels, and the long-standing collaboration with a single vendor represent a boundary case of successful coordination. Other administrations may not be able to draw on similarly favourable conditions.

Despite these contextual specificities, several patterns can be identified that extend beyond the individual case. These include the interpretation of an integrated specialist platform as an emergent digital strategy, a shift towards a shared situational picture rather than parallel reporting lines, the application of a once-only

principle alongside the reuse of structured data, and the understanding of vendor lock-in as a governance challenge that requires active management rather than being viewed solely as a technical risk. What may be transferable is not the individual products or modules themselves, but the underlying platform architecture principles that could guide comparable initiatives. These include a clearly defined target architecture with a shared data foundation, standardised data capture and interfaces, contractually secured data sovereignty and export mechanisms, and platform governance that actively shapes further development and interface policies.

Further research could explore the extent to which similar platform architectures generate comparable reductions in administrative workload and improvements in strategic steering. It could also examine how integrated specialist platforms might, over time, be embedded into national infrastructures such as **SHAPTH** and into emerging data spaces. For the purposes of this paper, it is important to emphasise that the Saarland solution should be read primarily as an illustrative case, demonstrating a particular combination of integrated platform design, strategic orientation and supportive governance, rather than as a blueprint for direct replication in other contexts.

6. Conclusion and Outlook

6.1 Key Messages of the Paper

Using the example of Saarland, this paper has demonstrated how an integrated specialist platform can place drinking water surveillance on a fully digital, end-to-end reporting pathway. The four-dimensional compass highlighted the key effects of this platform architecture, ranging from a continuously updated situational picture at federal state level to operational

relief, improved inter-agency collaboration and a future-proof, interoperable data foundation.

At the same time, it became clear that this platform architecture also brings new tensions. A high level of integration simplifies case handling, notifications and reporting, and enables efficiency gains through automated workflows. However, it also increases dependency on synchronised interfaces and software versions. Its introduction may place additional burdens on authorities with limited resources. Situational pictures could be interpreted as performance regimes, and a high degree of integration inevitably goes hand in hand with vendor lock-in and restricted switching options.

Overall, this paper interprets the Saarland approach as an illustrative case, showing how integrated platforms can create genuine opportunities for strategic steering, operational efficiency and future data spaces. However, these opportunities are only sustainable if the associated risks are addressed deliberately and understood as design challenges within the platform's architecture, its contractual framework and its governance model.

6.2 Füllpunkt_Saar and SHAPTH as an Outlook

In the introduction, Füllpunkt_Saar was presented as a fictional transparency project. Citizens scan a QR code at a public drinking water fountain and view, on a Saarland government website, who is responsible and what the current water quality is at that location. The preceding chapters have shown that much of the technical foundation required for such a project is no longer utopian, but is already being put into place.

At the time of the Wasserhygienetage 2026, SHAPTH is set to go live in Saarland's local public health authorities, establishing a national digital data pathway for

transmitting drinking water analysis results.

The planned interface with the existing platform, scheduled for the third quarter of 2026, will allow analysis results to be transferred seamlessly into the shared system without breaks in the digital workflow. These results will be directly linked to monitoring programmes, interventions and reporting data. Over time, this will result in a fully integrated specialist and data pathway, from the laboratory to the situational picture at federal state level.

SHAPTH is the national digital exchange standard for drinking water analyses. It enables the structured and targeted transfer of laboratory results between laboratories, water suppliers and local public health authorities. It is based on a shared XÖV data format.

In Saarland, SHAPTH will be integrated into the administrative platform architecture in such a way that analysis results no longer arrive as XML attachments via email but are instead transferred directly into the integrated specialist platform. Against this backdrop, the thought experiment of Füllpunkt_Saar can be understood as a third layer within this pathway. SHAPTH provides the national channel for laboratory results, while the integrated specialist platform consolidates the administrative view of drinking water installations, samples and measures. A Füllpunkt_Saar portal could make a carefully selected subset of this information accessible to citizens and political leadership. The data displayed would be sourced from the platform and reviewed and prepared by the responsible public authorities.

To make such an outlook realistic, incentives are required in addition to technical infrastructure and architecture. One possible approach could be to support investment in public drinking water fountains through funding programmes, in

which operators commit to submitting all analysis results, including fully compliant ones, via SHAPTH, and consent to the reuse of the data for Füllpunkt_Saar in compliance with data protection requirements.

In this way, the platform architecture already in place would not only support reporting obligations and strategic steering at the federal state level, but could also, in the medium term, provide the foundation for modern, accessible and comprehensible drinking water transparency.

6.3 Lessons for Practice and Further Development

The Saarland case offers lessons that go beyond the specific solution examined. An integrated platform should not be regarded as a one-off IT project. Rather, it requires ongoing management that addresses processes, technology and collaboration simultaneously. The decisive factor is not the individual specialist application, but the administration's ability to operate a digital reporting pathway reliably over time, to adapt it to changing conditions and to continue developing it as needed.

One practical conclusion relates to the **handling of vendor lock-in**. While it cannot be entirely avoided, it can be made manageable through an integrated management system. This includes continuous process oversight for the business workflows mapped onto the platform, clear routines for release planning, change management and incident handling, and early consideration of migration scenarios. Organisations that document their workflows, understand data models, describe interfaces in domain-specific terms and regularly test export mechanisms reduce the risk of losing operational control in the event of disruption or system transition. Vendor lock-in remains a real dependency, but it can become a consciously managed and

governable space.

A second lesson concerns **standards and infrastructure**. The closer a federal state platform aligns with open formats and recognised reference pathways such as SHAPTH, the less it becomes tied to any specific technology. If data models, exchange formats and reporting structures are designed to integrate with national infrastructures and future data spaces, the addition of new components or eventual system replacement becomes significantly easier. Open standards do not replace platform governance, but they help ensure the interoperability of a functionally integrated platform.

Finally, the case shows that platform operation is also a question of **organisational and workforce development**. A platform architecture that transforms situational

pictures, workflows and data flows also reshapes responsibilities, roles and skill sets within both local public health authorities and the supervisory body. This implies that future development should be closely linked to training, role clarification and a shared understanding of how to steer such systems. It would also be beneficial to accompany further expansion phases of the platform and SHAPTH with light-touch impact monitoring, in order to track burdens, relief and steering gains in a transparent manner.

For other federal states and administrations, the key message is that integrated platforms are not simply technical solutions, but long-term design challenges. Those who invest early in platform architecture principles, governance structures, open standards and active management systems are more likely to turn vendor lock-

in into a viable foundation for building reliable data pathways, decision-ready situational pictures and scalable development capabilities.

On the fiftieth anniversary of the German Drinking Water Ordinance, the Saarland case is therefore not presented as a model to be replicated, but as an example of the kinds of strategic questions that arise when reporting obligations increasingly rely on digital and near-continuous data pathways.

Citation:

Rausch, B. D. (2026). Digital Reporting Pathways in Saarland's Drinking Water Surveillance: Opportunities and Risks of an Integrated Proprietary Platform (EN). Conference contribution. 34, Wasserhygienetage, Bad Elster.

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ABSTRACT: This paper shows how Saarland uses an integrated, proprietary specialist platform to transform annual reporting in drinking water surveillance into a near-continuous digital reporting pathway. This pathway also supports reporting to federal and EU levels and prepares for planned integration with the national SHAPTH infrastructure. A uniform platform across six local public health authorities and a connected federal state platform instance used for specialist supervision create an end-to-end data pathway that places reporting, routine supervision and crisis response on a shared data foundation. Methodologically, the paper combines a scoping-oriented literature review with a theory-informed compass comprising four impact dimensions. It situates the Saarland approach within a federal multi-level governance system and the digital maturity context of the Public Health Service (ÖGD).

The paper identifies opportunities such as a continuously updated situational picture, operational relief, stronger inter-agency collaboration and a robust data foundation for future requirements. It also discusses risks, particularly unequal conditions, governance and vendor lock-in. Finally, it asks under what conditions dependency on an integrated solution can be understood as a manageable strength for standardisation, interoperability and, potentially, citizen-oriented transparency.

KEYWORDS: drinking water surveillance; digital reporting pathway; platform architecture; Public Health Service (ÖGD); interoperability; vendor lock-in; open-source; SHAPTH; multi-level governance

NOTE: This background paper reflects the author's professional assessment and does not necessarily represent the official position of the Saarland Ministry of Labour, Social Affairs, Women and Health. The paper provides an analytical case perspective; references to systems, standards or actors are descriptive and do not imply endorsement, preference or legal assessment.

REFERENCES

- Al-Hussein, M., Alabdallat, W., Abu Rumman, M., Jawabreh, O., & Ali, B. (2023). Impact of e-government applications on reducing administrative burdens in delivering public service. *Information Sciences Letters*, 12(3), 1663–1671. doi:10.18576/isl/120350
- Ansoff, H. I. (1965). *Corporate strategy: An analytic approach to business policy for growth and expansion*. McGraw-Hill.
- Arbeitsgemeinschaft der Obersten Landesgesundheitsbehörden [AOLG]. (2025). *Whitepaper zum Einsatz von Low-Code-Systemen im öffentlichen Gesundheitsdienst*. Senatsverwaltung für Wissenschaft, Gesundheit und Pflege. https://gesundheitsamt-2025.de/fileadmin/Downloads/UAG_Digitalisierung_Whitepaper_Low_Code.pdf
- Baars, H., & Kemper, H.-G. (2021). *Business Intelligence & Analytics: Grundlagen und praktische Anwendungen* (4. Aufl.). Springer Vieweg. doi:10.1007/978-3-8348-2344-1
- Boockmann, B., Braun, H., Dillbahner, A., & Tonn, H. (Hrsg.). (2025). *Die öffentliche Verwaltung unter Transformationsdruck: Konferenzband des Netzwerks Bessere Rechtsetzung und Bürokratieabbau*. Nomos Verlagsgesellschaft mbH & Co. KG. doi:10.5771/9783748948933
- Bunger, A. C., Chuang, E., Girth, A. M., Lancaster, K. E., Smith, R., Phillips, R. J., Martin, J., Gadel, F., Willauer, T., Himmeger, M. J., Millisor, J., McClellan, J., Powell, B. J., Saldana, L., & Aarons, G. A. (2024). Specifying cross-system collaboration strategies for implementation: A multi-site qualitative study with child welfare and behavioral health organizations. *Implementation Science*, 19(1), 13. doi:10.1186/s13012-024-01335-1
- Chandler, A. D., Jr. (1962). *Strategy and structure: Chapters in the history of the American industrial enterprise*. MIT Press.
- Chuang, E., Bunger, A. C., Smith, R., Girth, A. M., Phillips, R. J., Miech, E., Lancaster, K., Martin, J., Gadel, F., Himmeger, M., McClellan, J., Millisor, J., Willauer, T., Powell, B. J., Dellor, E., & Aarons, G. A. (2024). Collaboration strategies affecting implementation of a cross-systems intervention for child welfare and substance use treatment: A mixed methods analysis. *Implementation Science Communications*, 5(1), 127. doi:10.1186/s43058-024-00666-w
- de Figueiredo, B. A., & Cortez da Cunha Cruz, M. (2025). How can e-government respond to the digital divide? Two case studies from Brazil. *Conference on Digital Government Research*, 26. doi:10.59490/dgo.2025.962
- Digitales Gesundheitsamt. (2026). *Digitalisierung 4.0 des saarländischen ÖGD (Digi 4.0 ÖGD SL)*. <https://digitales-gesundheitsamt.de/projekte/projektvorstellungen/verwaltungsmodernisierung-durch-digitalisierung-im-ge-sundheitsamt-des-landkreises-wittenberg-oegd-digital-1>
- Eibenstein, H. (2022). Wasser. In A. Sangs & H. Eibenstein (Hrsg.), *Infektionsschutzgesetz: Mit Trinkwasserverordnung* (S. 593–631). C.H. Beck.
- Eymann, T., Neubauer, M., Schreiter, M., Schick, D., & Stark, J. (2024). *Bericht zu den Ergebnissen der vierten Erhebungswelle zur Erfassung der digitalen Reife der deutschen Gesundheitsämter und anderer Institutionen des Öffentlichen Gesundheitsdienstes*. Bundesministerium für Gesundheit. <https://gesundheitsamt-2025.de>
- Fedorowicz, J., Sawyer, S., Williams, C. B., Markus, M. L., Dias, M., Tyworth, M., Gantman, S., Jacobson, D., Tomasino, A. P., & Schrier, R. (2014). Design observations for interagency collaboration. *Government Information Quarterly*, 31(2), 302–316. doi:10.1016/j.giq.2013.11.006
- Fritz, N. (2020). Intelligente Datennutzung für eine moderne Kommunalverwaltung. *Public Governance, Herbst/Winter 2020*, 12–13.
- Giest, S., & Samuels, A. (2023). Administrative burdens in digital public service delivery: The social infrastructure of library programs for e-inclusion. *Review of Policy Research*, 40(5), 626–645. doi:10.1111/ropr.12516
- Grubnic, S., & Woods, M. (2009). Hierarchical control and performance regimes in local government. *International Journal of Public Sector Management*, 22(5), 445–455. doi:10.1108/09513550910972527
- Guijarro, L. (2007). Interoperability frameworks and enterprise architectures in e-government initiatives in Europe and the United States. *Government Information Quarterly*, 24(1), 89–101. doi:10.1016/j.giq.2006.05.003

- Halling, A., & Bækgaard, M. (2024). Administrative burden in citizen–state interactions: A systematic literature review. *Journal of Public Administration Research and Theory*, 34(2), 180–195. doi:10.1093/jopart/muad023
- Huster, S., & Kingreen, T. (Hrsg.). (2022). *Handbuch Infektionsschutzrecht* (2. Auflage). C.H. Beck.
- Irani, Z., Abril, R. M., Weerakkody, V., Omar, A., & Sivarajah, U. (2023). The impact of legacy systems on digital transformation in European public administration: Lesson learned from a multi case analysis. *Government Information Quarterly*, 40(1), 101784. doi:10.1016/j.giq.2022.101784
- Janowski, T., Estevez, E., & Baguma, R. (2018). Platform governance for sustainable development: Reshaping citizen-administration relationships in the digital age. *Government Information Quarterly*, 35(4), S1–S16. doi:10.1016/j.giq.2018.09.002
- Kleber, S.-H., & Busskamp, R. (2011). *WasserBLiCk – ein GDI/INSPIRE-Knoten der Wasserwirtschaftsverwaltungen in Deutschland*. https://wasserblick.net/servlet/is/176376/AKG_Koenigslutter_digitaler_tagungsband.pdf?command=downloadContent&filename=AKG_Koenigslutter_digitaler_tagungsband.pdf
- Klemperer, P. (1995). Competition when consumers have switching costs: An overview with applications to industrial organization, macroeconomics, and international trade. *The Review of Economic Studies*, 62(4), 515–539. doi:10.2307/2298075
- Klenk, T., Nullmeier, F., & Wewer, G. (Hrsg.). (2025). *Handbuch Digitalisierung in Staat und Verwaltung* (2., erweiterte und aktualisierte Auflage). Springer VS. doi:10.1007/978-3-658-37373-3
- Kuhlmann, S., Wollmann, H., & Reiter, R. (2025). *Introduction to comparative public administration: Administrative systems and reforms in Europe* (3rd ed.). Edward Elgar Publishing.
- Landkreistag Saarland. (2022). *Geschäftsbericht 2021/22*. https://www.landkreistag-saarland.de/fileadmin/user_upload/Landkreistag/Geschaeftsberichte/2021-2022_Gesch%C3%A4ftsbericht_LKT.pdf
- Lourenço, R. P., Piotrowski, S., & Ingrams, A. (2017). Open data driven public accountability. *Transforming Government: People, Process and Policy*, 11(1), 42–57. doi:10.1108/TG-12-2015-0050
- Lundell, B., & Lings, B. (2010). How open are local government documents in Sweden? A case for open standards. In P. Ågerfalk, C. Boldyreff, J. M. González-Barahona, G. R. Madey, & J. Noll (Hrsg.), *Open source software: New horizons* (S. 177–187). Springer. doi:10.1007/978-3-642-13244-5_14
- Madsen, C. Ø., Lindgren, I., & Melin, U. (2022). The accidental caseworker – How digital self-service influences citizens' administrative burden. *Government Information Quarterly*, 39(1), 101653. doi:10.1016/j.giq.2021.101653
- Mintzberg, H. (1987). Crafting strategy. *Harvard Business Review*, 65(4), 66–75.
- Naundorf, F. (2021). Trinkwasserkontrolle digital und mobil. *Blickpunkt Öffentliche Gesundheit*, 37(4), 5.
- Nielsen, M. E., & Madsen, C. Ø. (2022). Stakeholder influence on technical debt management in the public sector: An embedded case study. *Government Information Quarterly*, 39(3), 101706. doi:10.1016/j.giq.2022.101706
- OECD. (2020). *The OECD digital government policy framework: Six dimensions of a digital government* (OECD Public Governance Policy Papers No. 2). OECD Publishing. doi:10.1787/f64fed2a-en
- OECD. (2024). *Digital public infrastructure for digital governments* (OECD Public Governance Policy Papers No. 68). OECD Publishing. doi:10.1787/ff525dc8-en
- Opara-Martins, J., Sahandi, R., & Tian, F. (2016). Critical analysis of vendor lock-in and its impact on cloud computing migration: A business perspective. *Journal of Cloud Computing*, 5(1), 4. doi:10.1186/s13677-016-0054-z
- Peeters, R., & Widlak, A. (2018). The digital cage: Administrative exclusion through information architecture – The case of the Dutch civil registry's master data management system. *Government Information Quarterly*, 35(2), 175–183. doi:10.1016/j.giq.2018.02.003
- Rausch, B. D., & Wagner, L. (2025). Vom Jahresbericht zur Echtzeitüberwachung: Wie das Saarland seine Trinkwasserqualität mit digitaler Vernetzung effizienter überwacht. Ursprünglich veröffentlicht in energie | wasser-praxis, 76(5). ISSN 1436-6134. [Zenodo](https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.15240415).doi:10.5281/zenodo.15240415

- Reeder, B., Hills, R. A., Turner, A. M., & Demiris, G. (2014). Participatory design of an integrated information system design to support public health nurses and nurse managers. *Public Health Nursing, 31*(2), 183–192. doi:10.1111/phn.12081
- Schmeling, J., Marx, A., & Kurrek, H. (2019). *Evidenzbasiert steuern: Die integrierte Nutzung von Verwaltungsdaten* (1. Auflage). Kompetenzzentrum Öffentliche IT, Fraunhofer-Institut für Offene Kommunikation FOKUS.
- Schopp, N., Schüler, C., Tondorf, V., & Schüller, L. (2022). Lagebild Bevölkerungsverhalten für ein effektives Krisenmanagement. *Bundesgesundheitsblatt – Gesundheitsforschung – Gesundheitsschutz, 65*(10), 1067–1072. doi:10.1007/s00103-022-03583-2
- Shostak, R., Alessandro, M., Diamond, P., Mosqueira, E., & Lafuente, M. (2023). *The center of government, revisited: A decade of global reforms* (IDB Monograph No. 1113). Inter-American Development Bank. doi:10.18235/0004994
- Stoi, R., & Dillerup, R. (2022). *Unternehmensführung: Erfolgreich durch modernes Management & Leadership* (6. Aufl.). Verlag Franz Vahlen.
- Svoboda, J. (2022). Public procurement and vendor lock-in within the area of data migration: Ex post measures from selected legal regimes of direct applicability and their effectiveness in achieving data migration. *Milan Law Review, 3*(1), 116–164. doi:10.54103/milanlawreview/18741
- Vest, J. R., Kirk, H. M., & Issel, L. M. (2012). Quality and integration of public health information systems: A systematic review focused on immunization and vital records systems. *Online Journal of Public Health Informatics, 4*(2), ojphi.v4i2.4198. doi:10.5210/ojphi.v4i2.4198
- Whittington, R., Angwin, D., Regnér, P., Johnson, G., & Scholes, K. (2023). *Exploring strategy: Text and cases* (13th ed.). Pearson.
- Wimmer, M. A., & Marinov, B. (2017, 23. Februar). SCOOP4C: Reducing administrative burdens for citizens through once-only – Vision & challenges. *Jusletter IT*. https://jusletter-it.weblaw.ch/issues/2017/IRIS/scoop4c--reducing-ad_594387a002.html